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Sensor-Based Smart Metering with PID Control for Energy Theft Detection and Distribution Optimization

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ABSTRACT

The best and most advanced type of end-user payment and energy management plan device for electricity is a smart electricity prepaid meter. The main issue that power distribution service providers want to address is non-technical losses due to inefficiencies associated with the metering system. Unlike the traditional estimated billing methodology, this technique makes electricity use easily accountable and equitable to both consumers and power service providers. To lessen the frequency of electricity meter tampering, this study aims to develop a smarter prepaid meter. To the power distribution service providers, low revenue collection due to non-technical losses, especially tampering with electricity meters, is the main obstacle. By gaining illegal access to prepaid meters, electricity thieves can alter the proper power flow between the customer and the service provider and evade paying for electricity. The proportional integral derivative (PID) controller and a voltage sensor are the tools used to address this issue. When comparing the PID controller in closed and open loops, the products or results from each evaluation indicate that the closed-loop got 0.5 error rate while the open-loop got 0.85 error rate. Analogue meter efficiency was 65%, while smart meter system without PID got 86% efficiency. 93% efficiency being the highest was recorded with the use of smart meter system with PID. The research policy employed the strict evaluation of the sensor, the proportional integral derivative controller associated with the prepaid meter and the meter tamper response for improved distribution efficiency.

Keywords:- *Energy theft, Meter Tampering, Prepaid meter, Sensor, Proportional Integral Derivative Controller, Smart system*

INTRODUCTION

For electricity distribution companies, energy theft is usually a significant non-technical loss known as commercial loss. Thomas Edison established an electric company and energy theft was a problem soon after. In 1886, Edison was accused by the Daily Yellowstone Journal of having "many unprincipled persons avail themselves of the opportunity to steal electricity" by tapping into the wires upstream of the electrical meter.

The primary cause of non-technical losses is meter tampering. Smart meters are becoming a valuable and well-liked remedy for the rising issue of electrical energy theft. Digital gadgets called smart meters track and measure electricity consumption at the customer level, enabling energy suppliers to identify any irregularities or indications of fraud. Utility companies face significant non-technical losses due to electrical energy theft, which can be better prevented by employing smart meters.

An electrical energy meter is considered to have been tampered with if it has been altered, manipulated, or modified in any way that produces readings that are not accurate. The purpose of this is to lower or prevent the amount of electricity that the customer is billed for. This unlawful practice results in non-technical losses, which are a significant issue in the energy sector. One can tamper with meters in a number of ways.

The most popular technique is hooking or bypassing the meter, in which the electrical

load is connected to the system directly by the consumer. According to Muralidhara and Hegde [1], the application of IOT is a way to close the device gap in energy information. Without interfering with operations, the devices are able to measure electrical appliances and the main. In the same vein, Sultan *et al.* [2] presented a different method for calculating the energy consumption billing.

RELATED WORKS

GSM module is intended to be implemented, sending all data via the mobile network. Azmi *et al.* [3] introduced the energy meter simulation that measures electric parameters. One tool that is crucial in measuring each consumer's home energy utilized is an energy meter. A variety of load types, such as resistive loads and others were examined in order to assess the performance of energy meters. The detrimental effects of the practice of meter tampering were examined in their work [4].

A system comprising an ARM processor, an ACS 712 30-A range current sensor, and other sensitive devices was presented in their work for the prevention of energy theft [5]. Monitoring and detection in real-time was developed [6].

One of the main areas of attention is the implementation of suitable security measures for error checking, access control, privacy and encryption, and data validation. Procedures for installations must be appropriate and safe. The perimeter of smart meters should be frequently accessed

because often times communication port is compromised in the absence of sensors.

Hackers do not always need to be present to carry out physical proximity attacks; an accomplice intruder can be used instead. In order to protect sensors from physical attacks, cryptography can be used to integrate core security services. Only when specific conditions are fulfilled, some of which include the following, can the smart meter network reach its objectives [7]. An advanced communication and distribution system is used by a smart grid, a contemporary electric power network for the provision of electricity with better efficiency.

Unlike conventional meters, which record the full monthly consumption data, the smart meter harvests and send energy consumption data to the control center on a periodic basis (usually with a 15-minute resolution) [8]. Through enhanced smart electricity metering in power distribution systems with sensors, electricity theft may be eradicated. Power distribution companies are facing impending insolvency as a result of preventable revenue losses from meter tampering.

For the purpose of increased efficiency, a system that can transmit data between personal computer and smart card is necessary [9]. In the same vein, Uko [10] maintained that the meter generally transmits the data in half duplex mode. It was also discovered that IP-based controller can help in efficient online control of the energy the customer utilizes [11].

The objectives of this study are: to evaluate the voltage sensing module, design an energy meter tampering detection system, evaluate and control the detected tampered signal using PID controller to simulate the

anti-tampering prepaid energy meter using Simulink and video viewer to capture real time footage with meter proximity.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

The materials for this research include: proportional integral derivative (PID) controller, relay, video viewer, electricity meter, global system for mobile communication (GSM) sim with 800 modules, MATLAB/Simulink software 2021 version and Multisim.

Method

The method adopted in this study is the proportional integral differential Method.

Evaluation of the Prepaid Meter Voltage Sensor

The straightforward and incredibly helpful module lowers all inputs particularly, voltage using a factor of five based on the principle of voltage divider. The analog input pin of a controller can be used to monitor voltages that are higher than what it can detect. For instance, a voltage up to 220 volts can be measured with a range of 0 to 220 volts. Convenient screw terminals for quick and safe wire connections are also included in this module.

The voltage sensor measures the potentials across the load. With the PID controller connected to its output, the voltage sensor is tied to the mains. The voltage sensor working principle is derived from voltage divider circuits. Nonetheless, it is fairly simple to interface the voltage sensor with any controller. Attach the voltage source whose voltage needs to be measured, Vcc and GND to the voltage sensor screw terminals. Attach the PID controller to the voltage sensor GND pins, respectively. The

expressions for the voltage sensor input and output voltages are:

$$v_{in} = v_{out} \times \left(\frac{R1}{R1+R2}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$v_{out} = \left(\frac{V_{in}R2}{R1+R2}\right) \quad (2)$$

So, the sensor sees the tampered meter as – input voltage due to the voltage divider rules. The meter tampered equation can be expressed as:

$$Tampered_{meter} = -v_{in} + v_{out} \quad (3)$$

Evaluation of Current Sensing

The alternating current was measured with a transformation ratio of 1,000:1. The output of the current transformer links up with the microcontroller ADC pin. Across the terminals of the current transformer is a 220-ohm small value resistor. One can calculate the root mean square value of current by multiplying it by 0.707. The transformation

ratio, 1,000, is then multiplied by this value to determine the true primary current.

The power, current, and voltage can be expressed as:

$$P = \frac{v^2}{R} \quad (4)$$

$$I = \frac{V}{R} \quad (5)$$

$$V = I \times R \quad (6)$$

Energy Theft and Meter Tampering Detection System

A voltage sensor technique is used by the prepaid antisystem to detect tampering. The voltage divider rule is used in this technique to help sense the meter behavior. The PID controller receives the voltage changes and uses them to control the power system and meter. The power station receives information from the system about the meter tamper status. However, Figure 1 level of control makes this system extremely intelligent.

Fig.1:-Multisim Circuit Diagram of the Electricity Meter Tamper Control System

Implementation of PID Controller

Proportional controller is very important in PID system. The implementation does not pose any difficulty and it is very easy for tuning. Figure 2 depicts the system where

the R(s) and U(s) are the input and output controllers respectively while the G(s) and C(s) are the transfer function and variable respectively. The error is designated as E(s) which is $R(s) - C(s)$.

Fig.2:- The PID System

To elicit an output higher than zero $C(t)$, the error $E(t)$ comes to play, then:

$$E_{ss} = \frac{1}{k} u_{ss} \quad (7)$$

where U_{ss} is the controller's steady-state output and E_{ss} the steady state error.

One can reduce the steady-state error with increased K . The forward path is assumed to

be devoid of integration in this situation. A basic plant integration in its simple transfer function would be used to approximate $G(s)$ for the electricity meter. As illustrated in Figure 3, $G(s)$ would be roughly equivalent to the power plant's simplified transfer function.

Fig.3:-The PID Smart Meter System

Figure 3 scenario allows for zero steady state error condition. The presence or absence of steady state error above zero depends on the system type and input type. Negative unity feedback systems are subject to the well-known guidelines. It is satisfactory that:

$$e(\infty) = \lim = \frac{sR(s)}{1+kG(s)} \quad (8)$$

In every unit-step input, $R(s)$ is considered as $1/s$ in Eqn. (8) so that:

$$e(\infty) = \lim = \frac{s/s}{1+kG(s)} = \lim = \frac{1}{1+kG(s)} \quad (9)$$

Also,

$$e(\infty) = \frac{1}{1+k_p} \quad (10)$$

Unit ramp input will consider:

$$e(\infty) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{s/s^2}{1+kG(s)} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{s^2+s^2kG(s)} \quad (11)$$

When velocity error is in place, then:

$$e(\infty) = \frac{1}{1+k_v} \quad (12)$$

When the input is parabolic, we have:

$$e(\infty) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{s/s^3}{1+kG(s)} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{s^2+s^2kG(s)} \quad (13)$$

When acceleration error is involved, we have:

$$e(\infty) = \frac{1}{1+k_a} \quad (14)$$

Steady state error and error coefficient are inversely proportional in each of the three scenarios. It is possible to reduce error while K is increased thereby increasing error coefficient. But raising K could cause instability. This research focuses on proportional control to achieve efficiency in customer service and prevention of energy theft.

Considering the open-loop transfer function, we will have:

$$G(s) = \frac{K(s+a_1)(s+a_2)}{s^n(s+b_1)(s+b_2)} \quad (15)$$

Simulink operation of the tampered meter control system was used to implement the PID parameters in Table 1.

Table 1:-PID Parameters

PID	k_p	k_i	k_d
1 st implementation	25	20	0.002
2 nd implementation	20	15	0.002
3 rd implementation	15	10	0.002
4 th implementation	10	5	0.002

A smart feature of the anti-tamper prepaid meter is the addition of a video viewer, which helps to transmit video footage of an intruder tampering with the meter while increasing the likelihood of lowering electricity theft.

As seen in Figure 4, the model's image serves as an input for the tamper system, recording any activity on the prepaid meter and sending it to the power station for documentation purposes after first reaching the video viewer.

Fig.4:-Prepaid Meter Image Viewer Simulink Design

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tampering Response

In order to help the controller to understand the meter condition, the sensor response tampering signal is displayed in the figure. Therefore, these signals are transmitted to the controller when the meter is being tampered with.

This signal is interpreted by the controller as a meter error, and the meter is then instructed to shut off. When the meter is closed, a notification that the meter has been tampered with is sent. As illustrated in Figure 5, this meter technology gives it an advantage over traditional electricity meters.

Fig.5:-Tamper Response

Figure 6 illustrates the PID controller's reaction to the tampered signal. When the electricity meter is being tampered with, the controller sends out a signal. The circuit diagram for the tampered sensing system consisting of the initial metering system

stage, is shown in Figure 1. It is constructed on the Multisim interface using op amps. To regulate the behavior of the tampered situation, the PID controller responds to this signal by turning off the entire power system.

Fig.6:-Multisim Simulation of the Response of the PID Controller Due to input Tampered Signal

Distorted Power Supply after Tampering

As electricity theft increases, the use of traditional meters becomes extremely wasteful because they are inefficient at controlling the situation. When the meter was tampered with, the result in this figure

clearly shows it. Through the tampered sensor, a signal is transmitted to the PID controller. Following that, the controller instructs the meter to shut off. The distortion of electricity caused by tampered conditions is depicted in Figure 7.

Fig.7:-Distorted Power supply

Smart Prepaid Meter Trip Off

Upon turning on the electricity, the meter was tampered with due to the high control characteristics of the PID. The system tripped the meter at that point. Additionally, the intelligent reality the meter informed the station that there was tampering.

According to the findings, the trip off occurred when the load was 90 kW, as shown by the records of the most recent incident. This enhances the system's intelligence by storing memories, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig.8:-Tripped off Meter

Output Voltage Response and Output Current of the Prepaid Meter System

Figure 9 illustrates how much output voltage is supplied to the loads. By standard in

Nigeria, the operational voltage range is between 220 and 240 volts. That is to say, the output voltage needs to be 220V in order for the loads to be driven or operative.

Fig.9:-Multisim Output Voltage Response of the Prepaid Meter System

Figure 10 shows how much current flows through the prepaid meter when there is a load.

It also shows the meter system output current. Figure 10 shows an output current of 3A.

Fig.10:-Output Current of the Prepaid Meter System

Power Factor

Figure 11 displays the power factor of the electricity utilized. The power factor of the electricity used is shown as 1.

Fig.11:-Power Factor

Electricity Load

Figure 12 illustrates that the actual electricity load prior to the tampering was 4kWh. According to the outcome, the electricity load increased from zero watts to four kilowatt hours prior to the intelligent

meter system being tampered with and shut down. Because of the advanced control system that was introduced, the intelligent meter system has demonstrated a higher level of protection against electricity theft.

Fig.12:-Electricity Load

Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) Control Responses

Figure 13 displays the error response of the open loop PID control meter. According to the results, open loop PID is the best option, but there are still certain problems. One of the open loop system's problems is that it

lacks feedback, which makes its output uncontrolled.

The outcome displays how many mistakes in place when the system is being tampered with. Additionally, it is noted that the error rate, as displayed in Figure 13 is 0.85.

Fig.13:-Open Loop PID Error Response

Figure 14 shows the prepaid meter's PID closed loop controller. The response error rate of the PID controller for a closed loop configuration is displayed. It is noted that

the PID in the closed loop configuration produces an accurate result because a feedback principle is being used to control the output.

Fig.14:-Closed Loop PID Control Error Rate

Table 2:-Output Behavior of the Smart Prepaid Meter under Operations

S / N	Resistance (Ohms)	Calculated Load (Watts)	Measured Load (Watts)	Vout (V)	Iout (A)	P.F	PID Open Loop Error	PID Closed Loop Error
1	1000	40.00	40.00	220	0.250	1	0.85	0.5
2	900	51.00	51.00	220	0.263	1	0.85	0.5
3	800	57.00	57.02	218	0.288	1	0.63	0.4
4	700	63.00	62.99	220	0.314	1	0.81	0.4
5	600	69.00	69.00	220	0.371	1	0.74	0.5

Load Comparison

Due to the controller and sensor used to lower electricity theft, the meter system with PID controller has the highest theft control efficiency, according to the results in Figure 15 which demonstrates the performance

efficiency of the PID controller. The findings indicate that the analogue meter system has the lowest efficiency of 65%. The smart meter system without PID has 86% efficiency, while the smart meter system with PID has 93% efficiency.

Fig.15:-Meter System Efficiency

CONCLUSION

With the following outcomes, the study was based on enhancing smart prepaid meters to prevent electricity theft through the use of sensors and PID controllers. An assessment of the voltage sensing module that uses a potential (voltage) divider to reduce any input by a factor of 5. As a result, we can monitor voltages higher than the controller's ability to detect using its analog input pin, an assessment of current sensing by measuring the alternating current with a 1000:1 transformation ratio bar primary current transformer. The PID controller was employed to assess and regulate the detected tampered signal.

The closed loop-controlled error rate is 0.5 percent, while the open loop-controlled error rate is 0.85 percent. The efficiencies are 65% for analogue meter, 86% for smart meter system without PID, and 93% for smart meter system with PID. The highest efficiency occurred with smart meter system PID incorporated. The simulation was conducted using MATLAB/Simulink, which expressed the goals of the study with precision and clarity.

Unauthorized access to meters can be addressed by introducing a video viewer technique that records real-time footage within the meter's proximity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the authors recommend further research on advanced control systems especially, model predictive controller (MPC) and advanced sensors with very high-speed response.

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